

Enhancing Malaysia's Energy Transition through Integrated CLEWs Nexus Planning

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Executive Summary

Malaysia aims to achieve 70% renewable energy (RE) capacity by 2050 and phase out coal by 2045, a transition that requires balancing interlinked climate, land, energy, and water systems. Using the CLEWs framework in OSeMOSYS, this study explores three pathways: Business-as-Usual (BAU), Energy Transition Target (ETT), and Climate Change Impact (CCI). The BAU pathway is cost-optimal but fails to meet decarbonisation goals. The ETT pathway achieves national targets, cutting emissions by 76% and reducing water withdrawals by 63%, though system costs rise by 64%. The CCI scenario shows that targets remain achievable even under flood-induced productivity losses, though cropland demand increases by 22,000 km². Overall, the findings suggest Malaysia's transition goals are technically feasible but will require structured financial mechanisms to manage costs and integrated climate risk assessments to minimise land-use conflicts between energy, agriculture, and industrial development.

1. Introduction

As Malaysia advances its commitment to a cleaner and sustainable energy future, the transition towards renewable sources brings both opportunities and challenges. While scaling up technologies such as solar, hydrogen, and bioenergy is central to meeting national decarbonisation targets, their expansion has far-reaching implications on land use, food security, and water allocation. Solar photovoltaic (PV) has been identified as the backbone of Malaysia's renewable energy ambitions, however, it is particularly land-intensive and risks competing with agriculture as deployment expands from the current 5.5 GW to the much larger potential identified in Malaysia's National Energy Transition Roadmap (NETR). Similarly, bioenergy development raises concerns of land conversion and high-water demand, which could affect domestic food production and other sectors. These interlinked pressures highlight the importance of adopting an integrated perspective that considers the climate–land–energy–water (CLEW) nexus in guiding energy transitions.

The purpose of this study is to examine the implications of adopting such a CLEWs perspective for energy transitions in Malaysia. Using the OSeMOSYS interface MUIO (designed by UNDESA), three scenarios are assessed: a baseline case with continued coal reliance, a transition pathway towards 70% renewable capacity by 2050 with a full coal phase-out by 2045, and a case incorporating climate change impacts on land use. The analysis evaluates system costs, emissions, land and water use, while also determining a least-cost optimal energy transition pathway to support a sustainable and resilient energy transition.

2. Methodology

This study implements the CLEWs framework within the OSeMOSYS modelling platform to construct an integrated representation of Malaysia's energy, land, and water systems. OSeMOSYS (Open-Source Energy Modelling System) is a bottom-up capacity expansion planning and optimisation model that supports long-term energy system analysis. It is fully demand driven, meaning that by specifying the required demand (in this case electricity, crop and water demand) for the horizon considered, the model identifies the optimal technology options that can meet this demand at the lowest possible cost. The optimisation focuses on selecting among the technology options based on their investment and operating costs, operational lifetimes, efficiencies, etc. while adhering to constraints such as renewable targets or emissions limits.

Building on top of the OSeMOSYS tool, this study incorporated a Climate–Land–Energy–Water (CLEW) systems approach to represent the interlinked resource flows across three domains: energy, land, and water, as illustrated in Figure 1. In the energy layer, primary sources considered include coal, gas, light fuel oil, solar, hydro, and biomass, which are fed into energy generation technologies such as thermal power plants, hydropower, solar photovoltaics, and biofuel-based systems to meet electricity demand. The land layer

distinguishes between cropland, built-up land, forests, water bodies, and other areas including shrubland, grassland, wetlands, and bare land. Within cropland, the two highest-producing crops in Malaysia (oil palm and rubber) are modelled, while sugarcane is used as a representative biofuel crop in the model, with all other crops grouped into an aggregated category. Each crop is further classified as irrigated or rainfed to capture differences in water dependency. The water layer accounts for precipitation, surface water, and groundwater, which are allocated across competing uses such as public consumption, agriculture, and power plant cooling.

The CLEWs framework was developed in stages, starting with data collection and preliminary energy model construction. Key energy datasets were obtained from the Starter Data Kits (SDKs) provided by IRENA, the World Bank, IEA, Asian Development Bank, and International Road Federation. The SDK provides a valuable starting point, particularly when detailed country-level data are not readily available, allowing the model to be built and tested while additional data are gathered. Following that, land and water modes are incorporated. Agriculture and water data were sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and IEA databases, while macroeconomic indicators such as GDP, were collected from the World Population Review.

Figure 1: Reference CLEWs System.

Once the energy, land, and water modules were established, interlinkages were introduced to capture competing use of resources across sectors. For instance, energy is required for agricultural activities (such as diesel use for crop production) and for water services (including pumping and treatment). At the same time, water resources are allocated between agriculture, public demand, and power plant cooling, creating direct competition. Similarly, land availability constrains both crop production and bioenergy

potential, while requiring water use for crop irrigation. Through optimisation, the model determines the most efficient allocation of resources across these competing demands.

To design feasible pathways for Malaysia's energy transition, three scenarios were explored.

(i). Business-as-Usual (BAU)

The Business-as-Usual (BAU) scenario represents a continuation of current trends, where coal remains a major energy source and the model optimises the system to meet the electricity demand driven by a GDP growth rate of 5.1% with minimum costs. Meanwhile, water demand is shaped by municipal and industrial withdrawals, growing at an average of 4.1% while crop demand follows population growth of 1.9%.

(ii). Energy Transition Target (ETT)

Building on the BAU scenario, the Energy Transition Target (ETT) scenario examines a more ambitious pathway, by enforcing national goals of 70% renewable energy by 2050 and a full coal phase-out by 2045. This was achieved in the model by setting the parameter "total technology annual activity lower limit" for solar capacity according to the National Energy Transition Roadmap (NETR) targets and "total technology annual activity upper limit" for coal.

(iii). Climate Change Impact (CCI)

The Climate Change Impact (CCI) scenario incorporates climate-related risks, specifically flood for this Malaysia case study. In this scenario, it was assumed that the flood event will reduce crop productivity. In the model, this is represented by lowering "output activity ratio" of the crops technology to compute that more cropland is required to produce the same crop yield. Table 1 presents the output activity ratios for all three scenarios, BAU, ETT and CCI, respectively.

All scenarios were solved with the same electricity, crop production and water demand as shown in Figure 2. Across all scenarios, the model evaluates system costs, emissions, land and water demand, and identifies an optimal energy mix, land cover and water use to support a sustainable and resilient energy transition.

Figure 2: Current and Projected Electricity, Crop and Water Demand for Malaysia from 2023 to 2050.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of this study are discussed from three key aspects: changes in electricity generation mix, the implications for system costs and emissions, and the impacts on land and water use.

3.1. Changes in Electricity Generation Mix

Figure 1 presents the electricity generation mix under the three scenarios. In the BAU scenario, the model selects coal as the dominant generation source throughout the planning horizon. The results suggested that this is the least-cost pathway for meeting Malaysia's electricity demand, mainly due to coal's relatively low fuel prices and the advantage of existing infrastructure. However, this trajectory does not align with Malaysia's long-term energy transition ambitions. The Malaysian government has sets out ambitious energy transition targets to achieve 70% renewable energy (RE) capacity and the plan to phase out coal by 2045.

Figure 3: Optimal electricity generation mix from 2023 to 2055.

Therefore, to assess the feasibility of meeting these ambitions, a second scenario, the Energy Transition Target (ETT) scenario was explored. In this scenario, national energy transition targets were applied as a constraint in the model by setting a “total technology annual activity lower limit” for solar capacity according to the NETR targets and “total technology annual activity upper limit” for coal. This constraint ensures the system reaches the 70% RE target, while simultaneously imposing an upper bound on coal generation to represent its gradual phase-out by 2045. The results from Figure 3 indicates a rapid expansion of solar photovoltaic capacity in the ETT scenario, with solar and gas forming the backbone of the generation mix. Coal-fired generation then declines steadily with a complete phase-out in 2045.

While the transition pathway delivers strong progress toward policy alignment, the total system costs in the ETT scenario rise by approximately 64% in relative to the BAU scenario. Nevertheless, the results also show an overall reduction in cumulative carbon emissions of approximately 76% as compared to BAU. From an energy system planning perspective, this trade-off illustrates the fundamental policy challenge of reconciling affordability with sustainability. Yet, the results also demonstrate that Malaysia’s stated renewable energy and coal phase-out targets are technically achievable within a least-cost optimisation framework, provided that required investments are secured.

3.2 Implications on Water Use

Beyond cost and emissions, the shift in the generation mix has direct implications for resource use, particularly water. Thermal power generation technologies such as coal and gas plants are water-intensive, primarily due to their cooling requirements. In contrast, solar PV requires negligible water during operation. Figure 4 shows that as the model phases down coal generation and scales up solar, water withdrawals for the power sector decline sharply. Results show a 63% reduction in water use under the ETT

scenario compared with BAU, highlighting how shifting to renewable energy can generate substantial co-benefits for water security.

Figure 4: Optimal water use for each scenario.

The third scenario explores the effects of climate change, focusing on the impacts of floods on crop productivity. Figure 3 shows that even under these conditions, Malaysia’s energy transition targets of achieving 70% renewable energy and phasing out coal by 2045 remain technically feasible. The overall implications for system costs, emissions, and water use are also comparable to those observed in the ETT scenario relative to BAU.

3.3 Implications on Land Use

While changes in water use highlight the benefits of shifting away from water-intensive thermal power generation, it is equally important to examine how these scenarios affect land use, particularly the competition between land for agriculture and renewable energy development.

Figure 5: Optimal land use for each scenario.

In scenario 3, the introduction of climate-related shocks increases the amount of cropland required, as lower crop yields necessitate a larger cultivated area to meet the same level of production. At the same time, the results also indicate that while solar deployment expands substantially, its land footprint remains minimal compared to agricultural use, suggesting that solar expansion does not significantly exacerbate land competition at the system level. However, one key limitation of this study is it does not account for site-specific land suitability. Incorporating land suitability constraints in future studies could reveal potential competition between solar expansion and cropland, as only a subset of land may be suitable for large-scale solar installations. Such pre-screening would provide a more realistic assessment of land use trade-offs under energy transition pathways.

4 Policy Insights

The results highlight several key insights for guiding Malaysia's energy transition. First, the results demonstrate that Malaysia's energy transition targets (70% renewable energy and phasing out coal by 2045) are technically achievable, even under the stress of climate change events such as floods. However, achieving these goals comes at a 64% higher system cost, highlighting the urgent need for structured financial support mechanisms to ease the transition and mobilize investment in 450 GW of solar deployment. Beyond costs, climate change poses additional pressures on land use. Floods, for instance, could increase cropland requirements by an estimated 22,000 km² due to reduced productivity (by 12% to 30%, depending on crop type), which may intensify competition between agriculture, solar expansion, and industrial development. To address this, policymakers should integrate climate risk assessments into land-use planning, ensuring that renewable energy deployment aligns with agricultural priorities and long-term water security. Future work should further assess land suitability for solar expansion to provide policymakers with more granular insights for strategic planning. Ultimately, these insights underscore the importance of coordinated, cross-sectoral policies to achieve a cost-effective, low-emission, and resilient energy transition.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that Malaysia's energy transition targets of 70% renewable energy and coal phase-out by 2045 are achievable under least-cost optimisation, even when climate impacts such as floods are considered. Transitioning to a predominantly renewable energy system significantly reduces emissions and water use, while moderately increasing system costs. The analysis also highlights interlinkages across energy, land, and water sectors, showing that careful planning can minimise competition for resources. Overall, the results provide strong evidence that coordinated investments, climate risk integration, and resource-efficient technology adoption are essential to achieving a sustainable, resilient, and low-carbon energy future for Malaysia.

References

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Appendix

1. Data-in-Brief

Table 1: Output Activity Ratio of Crops for each Scenario.

Crops	BAU	ETT	CCI
Palm Oil (Rainfed)	1.801	1.801	1.585
Palm Oil (Irrigated)	2.828	2.828	2.601
Rubber (Rainfed)	0.028	0.028	0.022
Rubber (Irrigated)	0.043	0.043	0.038
Biofuel - Sugarcane (Rainfed)	1.203	1.203	0.902
Biofuel – Sugarcane (Irrigated)	1.888	1.888	1.605
Other crops	0.578	0.578	0.405

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